

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/yrtph

A critical appraisal of existing concepts for the grouping of nanomaterials

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 28 July 2014

Available online 7 August 2014

Keywords:

Nanomaterials

Risk assessment

REACH

Toxic Substances Control Act

Grouping of substances

Physico-chemical characterization

Exposure assessment

Hazard assessment

Biokinetics

Characterization

ABSTRACT

The grouping of substances serves to streamline testing for regulatory purposes. General grouping approaches for chemicals have been implemented in, e.g., the EU chemicals regulation. While specific regulatory frameworks for the grouping of nanomaterials are unavailable, this topic is addressed in different publications, and preliminary guidance is provided in the context of substance-related legislation or the occupational setting. The European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals Task Force on the Grouping of Nanomaterials reviewed available concepts for the grouping of nanomaterials for human health risk assessment. In their broad conceptual design, the evaluated approaches are consistent or complement each other. All go beyond the determination of mere structure–activity relationships and are founded on different aspects of the nanomaterial life cycle. These include the NM's material properties and biophysical interactions, specific types of use and exposure, uptake and kinetics, and possible early and apical biological effects. None of the evaluated grouping concepts fully take into account all of these aspects. Subsequent work of the Task Force will aim at combining the available concepts into a comprehensive 'multiple perspective' framework for the grouping of nanomaterials that will address all of the mentioned aspects of their life cycles.

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Abbreviations: BAuA, Bundesanstalt für Arbeitsschutz und Arbeitsmedizin (German NIOSH); BSI, British Standards Institution; CARACAL, Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP (EU); CEIN, Center for the Environmental Implications of Nanotechnology (University of California, USA); CLP, classification, labeling and packaging (EU); CMAR, carcinogenic, mutagenic, asthmagenic, or reproductive toxin; ECETOC, European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals; ECHA, European Chemicals Agency; EP, European Parliament; EPA, Environmental Protection Agency (e.g. USA); EU, European Union; FP7, 7th Research Framework Programme (EU); GAARN, Group Assessing Already Registered Nanomaterials (EU, ECHA); HPV, High Production Volume; HTS, high throughput screening; IATA, integrated approaches for testing and assessment; ICCR, International Cooperation on Cosmetics Regulation; LDH, lactate dehydrogenase; MARINA, managing risks of nanomaterials (FP7 project); MoA, mode of action; NanoMILE, engineered nanomaterial mechanisms of interactions with living systems and the environment: a universal framework for safe nanotechnology (FP7 project); NIA, Nanotechnology Industries Association (EU); NIOSH, National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health; NM, nanomaterial; OECD, Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development; OEL, occupational exposure limit; OSHA, Occupational Safety and Health Administration (USA); PCA, principal component analysis; QSAR, quantitative structure activity relationship; RCC (-NI), Regulatory Cooperation Council (-Nanotechnology Initiative) (USA-Canada); REACH, registration, evaluation, authorization [and restriction] of chemicals (EU); ROS, reactive oxygen species; SI, Supplementary Information; TF, Task Force; UBA, Umweltbundesamt (German EPA).

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<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2014.07.025>

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1. Scope and background: the need to assess nanomaterials by criteria related to conceivable risks

As more and more nanotechnological products enter the market, the importance of adequately assessing nanomaterial (NM) exposure, biokinetics, hazard and risk is now widely recognized. Worldwide, different governments, authorities, international organizations and other institutions are developing policy frameworks and guidance documents relating to nanotechnology, as such, and specifically, to the safe development, handling and use of NMs. Generally, the following aspects are addressed as potentially influencing NM hazard: The properties and biophysical interactions of NMs, their specific types of use and exposure, uptake and kinetics, and possible early and apical biological effects (Fig. 1; Oomen et al., 2014a,b). However, the specific alignments and contents of guidance documents for the hazard and risk assessment of NMs differ from country to country or jurisdiction to jurisdiction.

It is expected that the safety of a substantial number of NMs will have to be assessed. This is mainly a consequence of the very broad definitions for ‘nanomaterial’ as they have been laid down, e.g., by the EU Commission (2011) or the United States – Canadian Regulatory Cooperation Council (RCC-NI, 2013a). Further taking into account the abundance of NM modifications in regard to particle size, shape, or surface properties, the need to perform separate or additional safety assessments of NMs as compared to their respective bulk material counterparts could result in full-blown testing programs for each individual NM. In terms of testing capacities, their realization would not be accomplishable within a reasonable timeframe. Additionally, ‘tick-box’ testing schemes are not justifiable on scientific grounds since they inevitably lead to the collection of large amounts of unnecessary data instead of

focusing on relevant studies. Such testing schemes also contravene the need to restrict animal testing in line with the 3Rs principle to replace, reduce, and refine animal testing (Russell and Burch, 1959) that has been implemented in European legislation (EP and Council of the EU, 2010). Concordantly, the provisions of the EU REACH regulation on the registration, evaluation, authorization and restriction of chemicals prescribe that animal testing may only be undertaken as a last resort (EP and Council of the EU, 2006).

The so-called ‘grouping of substances’ (or category approach) has been recognized as an important means to avoid unnecessary new testing: In this approach, closely related chemicals are considered as a group, or category, rather than as individual chemicals. . . [so that] not every chemical needs to be tested for every endpoint. Instead, the overall data for that category should prove adequate to support a hazard assessment. . . [and] must enable an estimate of hazard for the untested endpoints (OECD, 2014). For chemicals in general, technical guidance documents on grouping are available, e.g. from the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) or the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA, 2008, 2012a, 2013a, 2014; OECD, 2014). This grouping concept implies that some, if not all, information on the hazard of a NM can be derived from the respective bulk material, from molecules or ions of its constituents, or from similar NMs.

By contrast, to date, there is little experience with the specific grouping of NMs. Whereas molecules in solutions or vapors are usually distinct definable species, NMs and particles generally do not exist as distinct species. Instead, they are a population of primary particles and, preponderantly, aggregates and agglomerates of various sizes and different surface coatings. The composition of the NM surface and of the molecules adsorbed onto it influences the biokinetic and toxicological properties of the respective NM,

Fig. 1. Source-to-adverse-outcome pathway to derive the relevant physico-chemical (blue), exposure (yellow), biokinetics (green) and hazard (red) endpoints (from: Oomen et al., 2014b; reprinted with the permission of the authors).

and such interrelationships are affected by multiple parameters (Landsiedel et al., 2008, 2010, 2012a,b; Lundqvist et al., 2011; Monopoli et al., 2011, 2012). Therefore, NM grouping should not be restricted to the determination of nanostructure–activity relationships, but should take into account all aspects of the substance's entire life cycle. These aspects include the NM's *material properties* (e.g. size, shape, crystallinity) and *biophysical interactions* (e.g. generation of oxidative species), its *intended use* (and hence incorporation into the respective product and possible release therefrom), the *'external exposure' to the NM* (i.e. the dose level and physico-chemical form of the NM exposure outside the body), NM *uptake and 'internal exposure'* (referring to the NM's concentration and physico-chemical form at the site of action in the organism), and, finally, its *biokinetics and possible early biological and apical effects* (Fig. 1). Addressing all of these aspects to group NMs allows ranking NMs and streamlining hazard assessment to conceivable risks. Such an approach can be put into practice in concern-based integrated approaches for testing and assessment (IATAs).

A number of concepts for the grouping and efficient testing and assessment of NMs have been published or are under discussion in on-going national or international political incentives or scientific research projects. These concepts base NM grouping on their structure and material properties (and material functions), their exposure, uptake and kinetics, and initiating cellular or apical effects. In the present survey, the ECETOC (*European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals*) Task Force (TF) on grouping and IATAs of nanomaterials reviewed and evaluated available concepts for the grouping of NMs as far as they concern human health hazard and risk assessment. Environmental hazard assessment was excluded from the scope of the survey as was the hazard assessment of NMs developed for medical, pharmacological and pharmaceutical purposes.

As a starting point for the overview on NM grouping concepts, Section 2 presents and discusses definitions for the term 'nanomaterial' and related terms, and Section 3 summarizes existing policies or regulatory frameworks for nanotechnology related to the hazard, exposure, risk assessment and handling of NMs. Information is provided for the European Union as the operative area of ECETOC, and exemplarily as important economies with detailed provisions on NMs, the USA, Canada, Japan, and Australia. Section 4 outlines existing regulatory concepts for the grouping of chemicals, as such. Section 5 presents and discusses recent conceptual proposals and research projects addressing the grouping of NMs, and Section 6 provides referenced examples on how such incentives are being put into practice in NM hazard assessment studies. Finally, a conclusion is provided in Section 7.

2. Definitions related to nanomaterials

To date, there is no uniformly accepted definition of what in fact constitutes a 'nanomaterial'. In 2008 and 2010, the International Standardization Organization (ISO) has provided overarching technical definitions for nanotechnology-related terms: 'Nanomaterial' is defined as *material with any external dimension in the nanoscale or having internal or surface structure in the nanoscale*, with 'nanoscale' defined as the *size range from approximately 1 nm to 100 nm* (ISO/TS 27687, 2008; ISO/TS 80004-1, 2010). However, as discussed in further detail in Section 1 of the [Supplementary Information \(SI\)](#) and summarized in [Table SI-1](#), different jurisdictions, committees, or societies have set up different definitions for the term 'nanomaterial', which further differ in regard to their determination of the 'nanoscale' (cf. [Table SI-2](#)).

All definitions of a 'nanomaterial' include the size range from approximately 1–100 nm, and none of the definitions take into account actual concerns in respect to the materials' adverse effects

on human health or the environment. The EU definition (EU Commission, 2011) is the only definition that includes natural or accidentally occurring nanoparticles, whereas all other definitions are restricted to 'intentionally produced, manufactured, or engineered NMs'. Furthermore, the different definitions are not consistent in regard to their mentioning of the state of aggregation or agglomeration of the nanoparticles, which in many cases however is the predominant state in relevant exposure scenarios: While some definitions do not mention this issue at all, others include aggregates and/or agglomerates, and one definition even explicitly excludes aggregates and agglomerates e.g. if the corresponding NM cannot be readily broken down into nano-objects. Two definitions specifically indicate insolubility and/or biopersistence – two further important aspects of nanoparticle characteristics, and only a few definitions take particle size distribution into account in their definition. Notably, since the EU definition is based on the size distribution of the *constituent particles of a material* expressed in number metrics (EU Commission, 2011; cf. SI), nearly every powder can be considered a nanomaterial as long as further guidance is unavailable on the term 'constituent particle' and on the dispersion method to prepare samples for measurement.

In summary, in spite of many years of intensive endeavors to agree upon an adequate definition for the term 'nanomaterial', far-reaching consensus on this term has not been achieved and is not foreseeable on the short- or mid-term. The EU has already announced the revision of its definition that was established in 2011: *By December 2014, the definition [...] will be reviewed in the light of experience and of scientific and technological developments. The review should particularly focus on whether the number size distribution threshold of 50% should be increased or decreased* (EU Commission, 2011).

The lack of decisive definition for the term 'nanomaterial' and the discussions about appropriate aspects and thresholds to be included allow the conjecture that scientifically justifiable parameters or thresholds for 'nanomaterials' which are generally relevant for safety assessment do not exist. All available definitions are based on material properties. While they are conceived and applied to found regulatory provisions for safety assessment, the definitions are not derived from toxicological evidence of a step-change in toxicity at 100 nm or any other single overarching material property applicable to all 'nanomaterials'. Specific concerns that have been recognized for specific types of NMs do not relate to their nanosize, but, e.g., to their respective chemical composition or shape. There is no evidence of a novel 'nano-specific hazard'. Instead, there is likely to be a more gradual magnification of the intrinsic hazard of increasingly small particles, e.g. in relation to surface area (Donaldson and Poland, 2013).

Since nanosize *per se* does not drive a specific toxicity (Donaldson and Poland, 2013), application of a general technology-based material definition to establish hazard information requirements of a broad spectrum of materials with different toxicologically relevant properties is likely to be incomplete or even flawed. It may result in performing the wrong tests or omitting relevant tests thereby leading to overestimation of certain hazards, while others remain undetected. Therefore, from the point of view of the ECETOC TF, all deliberations on NMs should take into account multiple perspectives, just as the grouping of NMs should address all aspects of the life cycle of the respective material within the context of its intended use.

3. Regulatory frameworks for nanotechnology and nanomaterials

Concepts for the grouping of NMs have to comply with regulatory frameworks and legal provisions that have been implemented for nanotechnology and NMs. Otherwise, they cannot be applied to

streamline hazard assessment to such information that is relevant in the given regulatory context. Therefore, this section provides an overview of regulatory frameworks for nanotechnology and NMs that have been implemented in different jurisdictions, specifically the European Union as the predominant business area of ECETOC and its members (Table SI-3), and additionally, as important economies from different geographical regions, USA (Table SI-4), Canada (Table SI-5), Japan (Table SI-6), and Australia (Table SI-7). As all tables reveal, most jurisdictions have published policy frameworks outlining their commitment to nanotechnology while at the same time confirming their dedication to ensuring a high level of safety of nanotechnological developments for workers, consumers, and the environment. As a rule, concrete provisions prescribing specific information requirements for the hazard and risk assessment of NMs have not been adopted in legal acts. Instead, NMs are considered to be generally covered by existing substance- and product-related legislation, and responsible authorities have issued initial guidance on the hazard and risk assessment of NMs or on appropriate risk management measures in the occupational contexts (cf. Section 2 of the SI and Tables SI-2–SI-7 for further details on the different regulatory frameworks and guidance published in the EU, USA, Canada, Japan, and Australia). As a rule, precise, detailed guidance on NM safety assessment is still under discussion. Therefore, all current initiatives addressing the different aspects of a science-based NM risk assessment can be considered in on-going regulatory activities.

4. Concepts for the general grouping of chemicals

In all jurisdictions, regulatory guidance documents are available addressing the categorization and grouping of chemicals as such, i.e. guidance from the European Union (ECHA, 2008), the US EPA in context of its High Production Volume (HPV) Challenge Program,¹ the Canada Substance Grouping Initiative, and the Japan HPV Challenge Program.² Likewise, the OECD has published guidance for the grouping of chemicals. First released in 2007 borne out of previous work from ECHA (OECD, 2007), on 14 April 2014, a second edition has been published (OECD, 2014; cf. Section 3 of the SI for further information on the OECD work related to NMs).

The OECD/ECHA analogue and category approaches are described as techniques for grouping chemicals. The **analogue approach** implies that grouping is based on a limited number of chemicals. Endpoint information for one chemical is used to predict the same endpoint for another chemical, which is considered to be 'similar', even though *trends in properties* (a term used in the OECD guidance to describe regular patterns of properties as a result of structural (or other) similarities) are not necessarily apparent. The **category approach** implies that chemicals can be grouped by physico-chemical, human health and/or ecotoxicological and environmental fate properties that are likely to be similar or follow certain trends. More members are generally present in a chemical category than upon application of the analogue approach, enabling the detection of trends across endpoints. The data for chemicals and endpoints that have been tested are used to estimate the corresponding properties for the untested chemicals and endpoints. Therefore not every chemical needs to be tested for every required endpoint. The overall category data and rationale should be adequate to support a screening-level hazard assessment (OECD, 2014; ECHA, 2008).

Different techniques are mentioned that can be applied to fill data gaps in a chemical category: For **trend analysis**, models are used that are based on the data for the members of the category. Likewise, (quantitative) structure activity relationships ((Q)SARs)

can be applied, and in **external QSAR models** the category under examination is a subcategory of a wider QSAR (To increase the regulatory acceptance of (Q)SAR methods, the OECD has promoted the development of a QSAR Toolbox³). **Read-across** is a technique used to predict endpoint information for one chemical by using data from the same endpoint from another chemical which is considered to be 'similar' in some way. In general, 'interpolation' (i.e. *the process whereby data from category members on either side of a data-poor category member is used to predict its hazard* (OECD, 2014)) is preferred to 'extrapolation' between category members (i.e. *the process where data from category members at one side of the category is used to predict the hazards of those members at the other side* (OECD, 2014)).

The OECD guidance highlights that application of the chemical category approach can be more efficient and accurate than a one-by-one assessment of single compounds: *The identification of compounds as members of a category provides an insight into the potential effects of the compounds that might otherwise be overlooked.* Thereby, also the evaluation of compounds that are often considered as 'difficult', in the sense that they can present technical difficulties when carrying out standard test protocols, may be improved (OECD, 2014).

Although chemical grouping and read-across are being widely practiced, the potential for these approaches to introduce additional uncertainty into hazard and risk assessment is broadly acknowledged (ECHA, 2008; ECETOC, 2012; OECD, 2014). The OECD guidance discusses a number of practical and scientific hurdles to consider when grouping chemicals, such as *gaining access to good quality data that are required for the data gap filling approach or the level of mechanistic understanding required for specific endpoints to help inform the biological plausibility of grouping.*

In principle, all grouping concepts have to surpass the same scientific hurdles regardless of the type or size of the substances under evaluation. As summarized by ECETOC (2012) and Patlewicz et al. (2013), also for non-nanosized chemicals, comparisons of the spectrum of relevant physico-chemical properties of the analogue and target substances as well as their likely toxicokinetics and molecular initiating events are addressed as key parameters to perform and justify grouping. Likewise, all substances, regardless of their size, have to be assessed throughout their expected life cycle.

Overall, authorities and industry are still at a learning phase on how to apply grouping concepts for chemicals most appropriately (ECHA, 2012a,b; ECETOC, 2012). Patlewicz et al. (2013) highlight that difficulties remain in applying category approaches and read-across consistently in practice. They address scientific challenges in preparing scientifically valid and robust read-across justifications that build on the knowledge of the presumed mode-of-action (MoA) driving the endpoint(s) under consideration. Patlewicz et al. underline the importance of a clear rationale underpinning the respective analogue or category approach, and to evaluate analogues by general and endpoint-specific aspects. Data on toxicokinetics are addressed as a key piece of evidence to support justifications. Integrating knowledge on how chemicals interact with biological systems (i.e. their molecular initiating events) with knowledge on the responses they can elicit at increasing levels of biological complexity are addressed as a means to derive chemical categories that allow predicting longer-term effects. Notwithstanding, full knowledge on the pathway from initial molecular initiating event to the final adverse outcome is not considered necessary to build a chemical category (Wu et al., 2010; ECETOC, 2012; Patlewicz et al., 2013).

To introduce more transparency to the degree of read-across uncertainty, Blackburn and Stuard (2014) have proposed a

¹ <http://www.epa.gov/hpv/pubs/general/catgrfnl.pdf>.

² <http://www.env.go.jp/en/chemi/hpv.html>.

³ <http://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/theoecdqsartoolbox.htm>.

framework for calculating uncertainty within a data set taking into account the robustness of analogue data sets, the concordance of effects or potencies, and the severity of critical effects. By assigning available data to these categories, the level of uncertainty of an analogue-based read-across assessment can be assigned transparently, allowing standardization of read-across measures and facilitating consistency in read-across conclusions drawn by different risk assessors (Blackburn and Stuard, 2014).

5. Concepts for the specific grouping of nanomaterials

5.1. Activities promoting the grouping of NMs in the context of substance-related legislation

Specific regulatory guidance on the grouping of NMs has not yet been published in the European Union (or elsewhere). Also the second edition of the OECD guidance specifically excludes recommendations on the grouping of NMs: *At present, it seems premature to develop guidance on grouping specifically for NMs. Nevertheless, research efforts will pave the way for common approaches and frameworks to grouping NMs for purpose of hazard assessment in the future* (OECD, 2014).

However, different authorities have released documents referring to NM grouping (Table 1). As a rule, they outline general requirements for grouping and emphasize, e.g. the need for sound scientific justifications to support the application of read-across techniques. In the 2nd best practices report from the *Group Assessing Already Registered Nanomaterials (GAARN)*, ECHA (2013b) confirms the usefulness of grouping measures in fulfilling the information requirements for NMs under REACH provided that they are accompanied by a solid scientific justification: *It is*

insufficient to base the justification only on the NM's chemical composition, but further physico-chemical parameters such as aspect ratio, shape, form, solubility, surface area, charge, surface treatment, etc. should be provided to support a sound scientific interpretation of the similarities or differences among (nano)forms.

This best practices report (ECHA, 2013b) is based upon the evaluation of 3 registration dossiers including nanoforms and NMs, but without making specific reference to these dossiers or providing any other examples. It further recommends applying the general similarity rules (or 'criteria') specified in Annex XI of the REACH regulation also for the grouping of NMs, basing similarities on:

- Common functional groups;
- Common pre-cursors and/or the likelihood of common breakdown products via physical and biological processes, which result in structurally similar chemicals; or
- A constant pattern in the changing of the potency of the properties across the category.

The basis for the grouping should be used to define what characteristics a NM should have in order to belong to a category. The similarity rules might be used individually and are case-dependent. Nevertheless, a category or similarity may be justified on more than one basis, which will usually increase confidence in the category. The basis for the grouping will help show for which endpoints the grouping applies, and if it is adequate for all routes of exposure and durations of effects (ECHA, 2013b).

Furthermore, the 3rd best practices report from the GAARN (ECHA, 2014) generally emphasizes that registration dossiers should contain a *comprehensive physico-chemical characterization of the registered nanoform(s)* and underlines the importance of

Table 1
Activities promoting the grouping of NMs in the context of substance-related legislation.

Publication/activity	Key element of approach	Physico-chemical characterization	Exposure	Biokinetics	Hazard
ECHA (2013b). Best practices report of the ECHA Group Assessing Already Registered Nanomaterials (GAARN)	Importance of 'solid scientific justification' for grouping	Chemical composition alone is insufficient, additionally, e.g., aspect ratio, shape, form, solubility, surface area, charge, surface treatment		The likelihood of common breakdown products resulting in structurally similar chemicals; consideration of toxicokinetics for grouping	Constant pattern in the changing of the potency of the properties across the category
German Competent Authorities (2011). Position paper on nanomaterials and REACH	Waiving of testing for NMs by referencing between bulk and nanoform, different nanoforms, read-across between different substances				
Araki et al. (2013). ICCR Working Group on safety approaches for NMs in cosmetics	'Bridging toxicity approach' to extrapolate toxicity data between selected non-nano and nanoforms, or between different nanoforms of the same NM				On the basis of similar toxicity profiles in short-term toxicity studies, combined with genotoxicity and toxicokinetics, toxicity data extrapolation may be justified
Anzai et al. (2012). NanoDiversity Evaluation Scheme TM	Classification by directness of human exposure and production volume		NM uptake during intended use; special consideration of chemical substances		
US Canada RCC-NI, 2013. Report on the development of a classification scheme for NMs regulated under the US and Canada New Substances Programs	Recognize 'NMs of concern' that are likely to behave differently from their bulk or molecular counterparts and therefore require specific risk assessment	7 classes of NMs: CNTs, inorganic carbon, metal oxides, metals, quantum dots, organics and 'other'.	Classification of NMs by similarities in chemical composition is considered preferable for regulatory programs, which are based on traditional chemical frameworks		

knowledge on material properties and biokinetics for NM grouping: *Generating data on toxicokinetics might also be considered for grouping substances in relation to read-across approaches, or extrapolating from in vitro to in vivo situations* (ECHA, 2014).

In line with this recommendation, in November 2013, CARACAL, the meeting of the EU *Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP*, stated that with the current understanding of REACH, it is possible and even encouraged that different forms of the otherwise same substance are registered in a single dossier as long as it is scientifically meaningful to share data. Accordingly, a scientific justification is required for the application of read-across techniques between the different forms of a substance.

In a *position paper on nanomaterials and REACH*, the German competent authorities in charge of hazard assessment describe three conceivable scenarios for waiving of testing during NM hazard assessment, i.e. (1) use of data by referencing between the bulk and nanoform of a substance; (2) use of data by referencing between different nanoforms of a substance, (3) read-across between substances with different chemical identities (possibly various bulk and nanoforms) (German Competent Authorities, 2011). Approaches for grouping and waiving are recognized to be particularly important for substances having a large number of different nanoforms. The German position further anticipates that waiving will be rare in the beginning, but has the potential to increase to the extent that standardized tests show that results from substances in bulk form can be utilized for NM hazard assessment (German Competent Authorities, 2011).

In the light of the European Union marketing ban for cosmetic ingredients and products, the *International Cooperation on Cosmetics Regulation* (ICCR; a voluntary partnership among the health authorities of Canada, Europe, Japan, and the USA, with participation and technical support from the cosmetics industry associations of the four jurisdictions) *Working Group on safety approaches for NMs in cosmetics* has suggested a 'bridging toxicity approach' to extrapolate toxicity data between selected non-nano and nanoforms, or between different nanoforms of the same NM. Due to prevailing knowledge gaps, the use of read-across or categorization approaches based on inter- or intra-NM extrapolation are not considered feasible for safety assessment. However, on the basis of similar toxicity profiles in short-term toxicity studies, together with the outcome of genotoxicity and toxicokinetics, the extrapolation of toxicity data may nevertheless be justified (Araki et al., 2013).

Also with a special focus on cosmetics, the *NanoDiversity Evaluation Scheme™* published by Anzai et al. (2012) foresees classifying NMs (and determining information requirements) by the directness of human exposure and production volume. Accordingly, the NanoDiv™ grouping concept focuses on NM uptake and internal exposure: In the first step, NMs are categorized as to whether they are expected to enter the human body (due to their intended use), or not. The NM's production volume is addressed as further fundamental parameter: If the annual production or import volume of the NM is less than 10 tons, or the NM content of the product is below this amount, low volume exemption, as it has been laid down in, e.g., the REACH regulation, is applied to the product. (However, the authors acknowledge that this threshold value might not be appropriate for NMs.) If the annual production or the sales volume exceeds 10 tons, the NanoDiv™ scheme distinguishes whether the NM is used as a raw material or as a consumer-used product. In both cases, different sets of tests are required depending on whether the NM will be used as cosmetic ingredient, or not.

If the NM is not for cosmetic use, and end-users will not apply the NM directly to their skin, the NanoDiv™ scheme addresses the respiratory system as the main target organ. Anzai et al. (2012) foresee testing to be performed in tiers, beginning with *in vitro* screening assays and moving on to acute and subchronic *in vivo*

studies. Long-term testing is only required if the initial tiers provide an indication for, e.g., carcinogenicity or reproductive and developmental toxicity (Anzai et al., 2012).

If the NM is intended for cosmetic use, the NanoDiv™ scheme requires assessing eye and skin toxicity in addition to respiratory tract toxicity. Additionally, dermal penetration and genotoxicity are assessed in early-tier studies. If their results indicate that additional long-term testing is necessary, either transdermal or carcinogenicity testing, or both, are performed. Based on the results of the early tiers, reproductive and developmental toxicity tests by inhalation are also carried out if necessary (Anzai et al., 2012). Of note, however, Anzai et al. do not address that, in accordance with the EU cosmetic products regulation (EP and Council of the EU, 2009), animal studies may not be performed for the human hazard assessment of cosmetic ingredients or products. Furthermore, to date relevant transdermal penetration of NMs that are intended for use in, e.g., sunscreen lotions has neither been observed in intact or sunburned skin, either *in vitro* or *in vivo* (Monteiro-Riviere et al., 2011).

In respect to the *new substances programs of Canada and the United States*, RCC-NI (2013a) published a draft report on the development of a classification scheme for NMs regulated under these programs. The classification scheme aims at recognizing 'NMs of concern' that are defined as NMs, which are likely to behave differently on the nanometer scale than their bulk or molecular counterparts and therefore require specific risk assessment: *The purpose of the classification scheme is to develop a framework to (1) identify which classes of NMs typically require nanospecific considerations in risk assessment; and (2) support the selection of appropriate analogue and/or read-across information for substance-specific risk assessments for NMs. In addition, the scheme aims at highlighting the type of information needed for characterization of the NMs within each class... The classification system is intended to be continually refined... as more scientific knowledge becomes available* (RCC-NI, 2013a).

For the time being, RCC-NI (2013a) addresses classification of NMs by similarities in chemical composition as preferable for regulatory programs, which are based on traditional chemical frameworks. By contrast, grouping according to toxicological information is not yet considered possible. Accordingly, the RCC-NI proposes a chemical classification scheme for NMs distinguishing between 7 classes of NMs, i.e. CNTs, inorganic carbon, metal oxides, metals, quantum dots, organics and 'other'. For each class, specific physico-chemical parameters are listed that are relevant for the respective sub-classifications (RCC-NI, 2013a). Furthermore, the RCC-NI (2013b) developed a scheme for focusing concerns and additional testing requirements for novel nanoparticles (Fig. 2).

5.2. Concepts for the grouping of nanomaterials for occupational safety assessment

Specific legal provisions setting information requirements for nanomaterial hazard assessment are largely unavailable. Scientists from different national health authorities and committees have published frameworks for nanomaterial safety assessment. A number of these frameworks include algorithms to broadly group NMs by common denominators (Table 2). As suggested in the respective publications, these algorithms can be applied to prioritize NMs for testing and for assessing e.g. occupational or consumer-related hazards.

The classification scheme of the *British Standards Institute* categorizes NM types into four groups that combine physico-chemical properties of the NMs and toxic effects reported for their non-nanosized counterparts, i.e. (i) fibrous NMs; (ii) NMs whose non-nanosized counterparts are already classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic, asthmagenic or reproductive toxins (CMAR); (iii) insoluble or poorly soluble NMs that are neither classified as

Fig. 2. Schematic for focusing concerns for novel nanoparticles (from: RCC-NI, 2013b; reprinted with the permission of the authors).

Table 2
Concepts for the grouping of nanomaterials for occupational safety assessment.

Activity	Key element of approach	Definition of 4 different classes of nanomaterials, based upon			
		Solubility	Biopersistence; low toxicity	Biopersistence; higher toxicity	High aspect ratio
British Standards Institute; cf. https://nanohub.org/groups/gng/guidelines	Combine physico-chemical properties of the NMs and toxic effects reported for their non-nanosized counterpart; relate OELs to the OELs of the bulk counterparts	Soluble NMs that are not assigned to any other category	Insoluble or poorly soluble NMs that are neither classified as fibrous, nor CMAR	NMs whose non-nanosized counterparts are already classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic, asthmagenic or reproductive toxins (CMAR)	Fibrous NMs
BAuA (2013)	NM hazard assessment should at least be based on effects induced due to specific chemical composition and on effects caused by biopersistence	Soluble NMs	Biopersistent NMs without inherent toxicity (granular biopersistent particles that possibly inducing pulmonary inflammation)	Biopersistent NMs with specific toxicity (i.e. release of toxic ions, activity of chemical functional groups, catalytic activity)	Biopersistent, fibrous NMs
Kuempel et al. (2012) from US NIOSH	Categorization based upon toxicological MoAs; suggest 'benchmark' reference substances for each MoA class for which full data set will be available and to compare limited data sets of further NMs against benchmark chemicals	Higher solubility particles shedding toxic ions that can reach systemic tissues	Poorly soluble, low-toxicity particles, where surface area dose of the inhalable particles determines toxicity	Poorly soluble, high-toxicity particles where reactive particle surface area dose determines toxicity	Fibrous particles (toxicity related to biopersistence, particle migration to the lung pleura, genotoxicity)
DHHS (NIOSH) (2012) control banding scheme	Develop control banding scheme to select from among a limited set of available exposure control techniques those that will most effectively protect the health of workers				

fibrous, nor CMAR; and (iv) soluble NMs that are not assigned to any other category (cf. BSI Published Document (PD) 6699-2, Nanotechnologies – Part 2: Guide to safe handling and disposal of manufactured NMs⁴). The BSI standard is one of the first documents to suggest OELs for the respective groups of NMs, i.e. 0.01 fibers/mL for fibrous NMs; 0.1 of the existing OEL for CMAR NMs; 0.066 of the existing OEL for insoluble NMs; and 0.5 of the existing OEL for the soluble NMs.

The German Federal Institute for Occupational Safety and Health has published an *Announcement regarding hazardous substances* for NMs that specifically addresses inhalation as the predominant route of exposure (BAuA, 2013). This announcement requires at least basing hazard assessment on effects induced due to the specific chemical composition of the NMs and on effects caused by biopersistence of the object (measured by the degree of water solubility). Taking into account toxicological properties, material properties (shape and structure) and biopersistence, the announcement foresees four groups of substances, i.e. soluble NMs, biopersistent NMs with specific toxicological properties (i.e. release of toxic ions, activity of chemical functional groups, and catalytic activity), biopersistent NMs without toxicological properties (granular biopersistent particles that may possibly induce pulmonary inflammation), and biopersistent, fibrous NMs (BAuA, 2013; Packroff, 2013).

Hartwig (2013), chairing the *Commission for the investigation of health hazards of chemical compounds in the work area of the German Research Foundation* suggests the same scheme to group NMs by specific chemical properties and additionally takes into account whether NMs are intended for medicinal use. As regards grouping NMs by area of use, the German Federal Environmental Agency published a report whose actual goal was to assess impacts of an European register of products containing NMs (UBA, 2014). In this report, a classification framework is presented to group products containing NMs into the following sectors or categories: substances, cosmetics, health care, food & feed, coatings & inks, cleaning & disinfection, rubber products, building & construction, textiles, paper products, and complex objects & other products.

Consistent with the NM categorization scheme proposed by BAuA (2013), Kuempel et al. (2012) from the US NIOSH propose four MoA classes for a broad categorization of NMs, i.e. (i) higher solubility particles shedding toxic ions that can reach systemic tissues; (ii) poorly soluble, low-toxicity particles, where surface area dose of the inhalable particles determines toxicity; (iii) poorly soluble, high-toxicity particles where reactive particle surface area dose determines toxicity; (iv) fibrous particles for which toxicity is presumably related to biopersistence, particle migration to the lung pleura, and genotoxicity.

Kuempel et al. (2012) suggest selecting ‘benchmark’ materials for each of the above-mentioned MoA categories. For such benchmark materials, sufficient dose–response data for quantitative risk assessment should be available. New NMs are classified in accordance to the hazard and risk estimates of the corresponding benchmark substances exhibiting the same MoA. A key challenge in setting MoA-based classes and sub-classes recognized by Kuempel et al. is obtaining adequate dose–response data to systematically evaluate the physico-chemical factors influencing the biological activities of NMs.

In the absence of occupational exposure limits (OELs) for most NMs, the US NIOSH has published guidance on developing an occupational control scheme, i.e. the so-called control banding (DHHS (NIOSH), 2012). The ultimate goal of control banding is to select from among a limited set of available exposure control techniques those that will most effectively protect the health of workers

(Gordon et al., 2014). Such techniques, ranked by their purpose to manage minor to severe hazards, cover (i) application of good industrial hygiene practices and general ventilation; (ii) application of engineering controls (e.g. local exhaust ventilation); (iii) process enclosure; and (iv) seeking expert advice (DHHS (NIOSH), 2012). Developing OELs for representative benchmark particles within each of the above-mentioned MoA categories would provide a basis for linking the health effects data of NMs with limited data to the appropriate exposure control bands (Kuempel et al., 2012).

Similarly, the research organization TNO – *Innovation for Life*, located in the Netherlands, published the risk-banding tool ‘Stoffenmanager Nano vs. 1.0’ to prioritize NM health risks by combining available NM hazard information with a qualitative estimate of potential worker inhalation exposure (van Duuren-Stuurman et al., 2012). Already in 2008, the Swiss Federal Office for Public Health released a precautionary matrix for synthetic NMs serving to identify potentially hazardous NMs. This matrix is based on the assumption that – throughout the NM’s life cycle – risks can only arise if particles being on the nanoscale in two or three dimensions (i.e. nanorods or nanoparticles) can be released (Höck et al., 2008). Also the Quebecois Research Institute for Health and Occupational Safety published a control banding tool for NMs similar to the one from the US NIOSH that groups NMs by hazard and emission potential to help define action plans in the occupational setting (Ostiguy et al., 2010; Riediker et al., 2012).

5.3. Concepts for the grouping of NMs presented in different research projects

A plenitude of research projects funded with public or private resources focus on NM hazard assessment, and a number of these projects also address the grouping of NMs. The grouping considerations published in the context of the following EU-funded projects (as well as of the Nanotechnology Industries Association) complement each other and therefore are presented and discussed jointly in this section (cf. Table 3):

- The project **MARINA** (www.marina-fp7.eu), funded under the European Commission’s 7th Research Framework Programme (FP7), has the scope to develop and validate risk assessment and risk management methods for NMs (van Tongeren et al., 2013).
- The **NanoSafety Cluster** (www.nanosafetycluster.eu) is a European Commission initiative to maximize the synergies between existing FP6 and FP7 projects addressing all aspects of nanosafety (Savolainen et al., 2013; Oomen et al., 2014a, 2014b).
- The FP7 project **ITS-NANO** (www.its-nano.eu) aimed at developing a research strategy concerning the interactions of NMs with biological systems in order to intelligently design nanosafety evaluation and risk assessment strategies, identify high risk materials, and implement effective strategies to counter the risks (Stone et al., 2013, 2014).
- The overarching objective of the FP7-funded **NanoMILE project** (<http://nanomile.eu-vri.eu>) is to formulate a paradigm for the mode(s) of interaction between NMs and organisms or the environment (Lynch et al., 2014).
- The FP7-funded **NanoSolutions project** (nanosolutionsfp7.com) whose overarching aim is to provide a means to develop a safety classification for engineered NMs based on an understanding of their interactions with living organisms at molecular, cellular and organism levels.

As discussed in further detail by Oomen et al. (2014a,b), more than a dozen material properties and biophysical interactions of NMs have been identified that could potentially contribute to hazardous effects. Some of these characteristics also influence

⁴ <https://nanohub.org/groups/gng/guidelines> and: <http://ohsonline.com/articles/2008/02/bsi-british-standards-takes-lead-in-nano-guidance.aspx>.

Table 3
Concepts for the grouping of nanomaterials presented in different research projects or put into practice in the context of research activities.

Project/publication	Overall grouping concept	Key element of approach	Addressed aspects of nanomaterial properties throughout its life cycle			
			Ph.-ch.	Exp.	Biokin.	Haz.
MARINA (van Tongeren et al., 2013); NanoSafety Cluster (Oomen et al., 2014a,b)	NMs can be grouped by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Their production, use and release (throughout the life cycle) · The physico-chemical characteristics of a NM, which can be different in different life cycle stages (e.g. release and external exposure of organisms) · The physico-chemical characteristics of a NM, which can be different in different life cycle stages (e.g. release and external exposure of organisms) · The uptake, biodistribution, and biopersistence (biokinetics) of a NM in an organism and the physico-chemical characteristics of a NM inside the organism at different target sites · The early and apical biological effects 	Grouping should take into account all aspects of the NM during its life cycle. The grouping concept is closely linked to IATAs, since both serve to recognize and refine concerns	x	x	x	x
National Industries Association NIA (2013)	Suggest a broad spectrum of criteria that might be used for the grouping of NMs, i.e. high aspect ratio NMs, rigidity, metal oxides, ion generation, ROS generation (reactive oxygen species), crystalline structure, organic/inorganic, softness/hardness, lipid/non-lipid, quantum effects, natural complex substances, inhalation studies		x			x
ITS-Nano (Stone et al., 2013, 2014)	The MoAs of NMs and how they relate to a defined set of physico-chemical characteristics is seen as crucial in developing grouping, ranking, or modeling tools	Physico-chemical, exposure, and hazard identification are key elements of NM risk assessment; these identities should be applied to group NMs	x	x		x
NanoMILE (Lynch et al., 2014)	Intrinsic (inherent) properties (e.g. shape, porosity, structural configuration and band gap); chemical composition (inherent molecular toxicity, charge, hydrophobicity and coating); and extrinsic properties (alterations in binding of biomolecules – interaction with media, formation of molecular coronas – and resultant biomolecule conformational effects (e.g. unfolding, receptor activation, membrane damage, fibrillation etc.))	Grouping strategy that interlinks key physico-chemical descriptors to predict nanoparticle toxicity as the sum of three quantifiable parameters capturing the diversity of MoAs	x			
Nano-solutions (2013)	Provide a means to develop a safety classification for engineered NMs based on an understanding of their interactions with living organisms at molecular, cellular and organism levels	Development of a computer program evaluating the properties of engineered NMs to predict their ability to cause health or environmental hazards	x		x	x
UC CEIN USA e.g. Nel et al. (2013)	Predictive toxicological approach using mechanism-based <i>in vitro</i> assays for high-throughput screening (HTS) of NMs	Address major mechanisms of NM toxicity				x
Lai (2012). US EPA	High-throughput screening NM toxicity testing paradigm	Select reference materials for different classes of NMs having unique physico-chemical characteristics, which may lead to different biological effects by different MoA	x			x
Shaw et al. (2008). Harvard Univ, USA	Perturbational profiling of NM biological activity		x			x
Cho et al. (2013). Univ. Edinburgh, UK	Mechanism-based predictive testing approach		x			x

biokinetic processes and therefore the fraction of a NM that reaches the target site in the organism, whereas potentially other – or another set of – material properties and biophysical interactions influence their biological effects. This can confound the correlation between one single material property and an apical effect. Oomen et al. conclude that due to the complexity of NMs, NM grouping should not be restricted to determination of simple nanostructure–activity relationships, but take into account all aspects of their life cycles.

Accordingly, NMs can be grouped by:

- Their production, use and release (throughout the life cycle);
- The physico-chemical characteristics of a NM, which can be different in different life cycle stages (e.g. release and external exposure of organisms);
- The uptake, biodistribution, and biopersistence (biokinetics) of a NM in an organism and the physico-chemical characteristics of a NM inside the organism at different target sites;

- The early and apical biological effects (Fig. 1).

In such a ‘multiple perspective’ categorization framework, a given NM is likely to belong to more than one group. To enable applying the grouping approach for regulatory purposes, grouping criteria need to be established that allow justifying the use of read-across measures to fill data gaps within the group. At best, such justifications should be founded on information regarding the MoA driving the endpoint under consideration (Oomen et al., 2014a,b).

Similar to the grouping considerations put forward by the German competent authorities or the US NIOSH, one purpose for NM grouping addressed in the EU projects is to rank NMs, i.e. prioritize for testing. During ranking, NMs are ‘assigned a position in a scale’, e.g. based on their potential for exposure (e.g. high dustiness) and/or high intrinsic toxicity. As such, ranking of different types of NMs does not necessarily imply a relationship between the NMs. NM grouping, by contrast, implies that the combined

NMs share a common attribute (Stone et al., 2013, 2014). Accordingly, ranking can be performed within groups of NMs, but also entire groups can be ranked (Zuin et al., 2011).

The European Nanotechnology Industries Association (NIA, 2013) suggests a broad spectrum of criteria that might be used for the grouping of NMs, i.e. high aspect ratio NMs, rigidity, metal oxides, ion generation, ROS generation (reactive oxygen species), crystalline structure, organic/inorganic, softness/hardness, lipid/non-lipid, quantum effects, natural complex substances, inhalation studies. This mixture of parameters encompasses the spectrum of criteria suggested by Oomen et al. (2014a,b).

NIA (2013) provide a practical example for the grouping of NMs in accordance with the 'ion release hypothesis': This hypothesis is based upon the assumption that, e.g., Ag NMs are of equivalent or lower toxicity than the corresponding silver ions – and that this is true irrespective of particle size or coating type. Accordingly, read-across from ionic Ag or nanoform Ag to non-nano Ag would be valid and conservative.

Oomen et al. (2014a,b) underline that NM grouping strategies are closely linked to NM testing strategies, i.e. integrated approaches for testing and assessment (IATAs). Both aim at determining the identical concerns and apply the same criteria to do so. In IATAs, 'NMs of concern' are identified based on relevant exposure scenarios and the physico-chemical characteristics of the specific NM during its life cycle. IATAs proceed through a number of tiers where, first, all existing, and subsequently, if necessary, newly gained, information on exposure, kinetics and hazard of the NM is considered taking into account its entire life cycle. At the end of each tier, all information gathered at that stage is evaluated to derive a more comprehensive conclusion. Step-by-step, concerns are refined, and the uncertainty about potential risks is reduced. This stepwise identification and refinement of concerns during hazard assessment automatically implies some form of grouping (Oomen et al., 2014a,b; van Tongeren et al., 2013; Stone et al., 2013, 2014).

The key elements of IATAs and concern evaluation are *flexibility* and *efficiency*. *Flexibility* implies the incentive to define the most appropriate information requirements that best address the respective concern. The key element *efficiency* refers to the goal to only collect those pieces of information that are really needed (van Tongeren et al., 2013). IATAs can stop at any given tier as soon as sufficient certainty on the conclusion to be drawn is obtained. If further information is considered necessary at the end of a given tier, specific tests targeted to the relevant concerns can be selected based on the information of the previous tiers applying increasingly specific tools from tier to tier to collect or generate information. While advancing to higher tiers, the total amount of data and their complexity increases, uncertainty is progressively reduced, and the assessment becomes more and more realistic and detailed (Oomen et al., 2014a,b).

An important challenge in developing concepts on the grouping of NMs is to enable simultaneously identifying and assessing the impact of different physico-chemical properties on the harm the NMs may induce. The NanoMILE project (Lynch et al., 2014) suggests a grouping strategy that interlinks key physico-chemical descriptors to predict nanoparticle toxicity as the sum of three quantifiable parameters capturing the diversity of MoAs, i.e. their *intrinsic* (inherent) properties (e.g. shape, porosity, structural configuration and band gap); *chemical composition* (inherent molecular toxicity, charge, hydrophobicity and coating); and *extrinsic* properties (alterations in binding of biomolecules – interaction with media, formation of molecular coronas – and resultant biomolecule conformational effects (e.g. unfolding, receptor activation, membrane damage, fibrillation etc.).

The NanoMILE approach is founded on previous work by Sayes et al. (2013) demonstrating the feasibility of grouping of NMs

based on combinations of related physico-chemical properties. Using principal component analysis (PCA) and linear discriminant analysis, Sayes et al. assessed which properties of a set of selected physico-chemical properties (engineered size, concentration, agglomerated size in water, zeta potential, pH and age of the suspension, and oxidant production) were redundant in terms of their detectable linear interdependencies across different silver, copper, nickel, zinc and iron NMs. Sayes et al. further assessed which features were best suited to discriminate between NM groups that were based on known similarities (e.g. potential for dissolution) or measured values (e.g. zeta potential, agglomeration in solution). As an outcome of these assessments, the seemingly homogeneous group of metal NMs could be further sub-grouped.

Similarly, Simko et al. (2014) address the following crucial material properties determining the 'effective dosages' reaching cells upon *in vitro* or *in vivo* test substance application: specific surface area, surface textures, surface charge (influencing particle absorption, corona formation and biokinetics), particle morphology (e.g. different shapes and aspect ratios of fibers vs. glomerular particles), band gap energy levels of metal and metal oxide NMs (affecting catalytic activity and ROS formation), and particle dissolution rate (affecting ion release). Also the FP7-funded NanoSolutions project is aiming at identifying and elaborating those characteristics of NMs that determine their biological hazard potential with the goal to develop a computer program that allows predicting NM human health hazards based upon NM properties.

6. Research activities putting NM grouping into practice

A vast number of research papers are available addressing NM toxicity *in vitro* or *in vivo*. Due to scientific shortages, e.g. in the study design, the physico-chemical characterization of the test substances, or the selection of appropriate dosages *in vitro* that reflect realistic exposure scenarios *in vivo*, many studies are of limited value in adding knowledge on the toxic potential of NMs (Landsiedel et al., 2014). However, a few publications describe comprehensive 'multiple perspective' approaches for NM toxicity testing that address NM complexity by making use of high-throughput screening platforms and computational tools for data evaluation. In the following, the work from A. Nel and co-workers (e.g., Nel et al., 2013), Lai (2012), Shaw et al. (2008), and Cho et al. (2013) is presented in further detail to show how NM grouping can be put into practice for NM hazard assessment (Table 3). NM grouping is not only applied to substantiate the interpretation of test results and to rank NMs, but also to support the selection of test methods and justify transitions from *in vitro* to *in vivo* testing. All of the evaluated approaches confirm the need to interlink different relevant material properties of NMs for NM hazard assessment. Furthermore, they provide initial indications how concern-driven IATAs that are founded on NM grouping might be applied for regulatory NM hazard assessment.

6.1. Predictive toxicological approach (e.g. Nel et al., 2013)

The University of California Center for the Environmental Implications of Nanotechnology (UC CEIN; USA), led by A.E. Nel, has developed a predictive toxicological approach using mechanism-based *in vitro* assays for high-throughput screening (HTS) of NMs. The HTS platform simultaneously measures a set of sub-lethal and lethal cellular endpoints reflecting important toxicity pathways for NMs, such as inflammatory reactions induced by Ag and ZnO NMs that shed toxic ions, surface reactivity-induced redox activity and ROS production for, e.g. TiO₂ NMs, membrane lysis elicited by partly soluble SiO₂ NMs, or fiber-like toxicity caused by high aspect ratio NMs, such as carbon nanotubes (Fig. 3). In

Fig. 3. Mechanistic injury pathways recognized for NMs (from: Nel et al., 2013; reprinted with the permission of the author).

the HTS platform, human lung epithelial BEAS-2B cells and rat alveolar macrophage RAW264.7 cells are submitted to cellular staining with fluorescent probes and high content epi-fluorescence microscopy, ATP, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), and tetrazolium salt assays, and inductively-coupled plasma-mass spectrometry analysis (detecting heavy metal ion release). Additionally, the UC CEIN HTS platform includes physico-chemical characterization studies and studies with zebra fish embryos (Meng et al., 2009; Damoiseaux et al., 2011; George et al., 2011; Thomas et al., 2011; Xia et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2012; Nel et al., 2013).

Of note, already in 1999, Rehn et al. from the University of Essen, Germany, described a multi-parametric *in vitro* testing battery using isolated alveolar macrophages for the screening of pulmonary effects of dust aerosols. By combining the results obtained for a set of independent endpoints (esterase activation, release of H_2O_2 , glucuronidase and LDH, induction of tumor necrosis factor alpha, and ROS generation), assay sensitivity and specificity could be improved in comparison to single endpoint cytotoxicity assays, and distinct toxicity patterns of different dusts could be discerned (Rehn et al., 1999). These mentioned endpoints cover the four basic principles of (nano)dust toxicity, i.e. ROS generation, release of inflammatory mediators, impairment of cellular function, cytotoxicity (Schnekenburger et al., 2009), and reflect the toxicity pathways covered in the HTS platform of the UC CEIN.

In the predictive toxicological approach described by Nel et al., the *in vitro* screening assays are evaluated to quantitatively assess dose- and time-dependent molecular initiating events and toxicity pathways that are predictive of *in vivo* adverse outcomes (which would then have to be confirmed in limited rodent studies). Data from the HTS platforms are provided in a multivariate context (e.g. concentration, exposure times, sub-lethal and lethal biological responses). Due to the complexity of the data, feature-extraction methods are applied for visual data interpretation. So-called 'heat-map clusters' provide ordered representations of data allowing to identify similarity patterns of large datasets based on homologous biological responses or linkage to physico-chemical properties. Data obtained with the HTS assays are evaluated to make predictions about those physico-chemical properties of NMs that may lead to the generation of adverse effects *in vivo*. Thereby, multi-parametric mechanism-based HTS approaches

combined with heat-map clustering enable the development of nanostructure–activity relationships and NM grouping (Damoiseaux et al., 2011; George et al., 2011; Liu et al., 2011; Rallo et al., 2011; Thomas et al., 2011; Nel et al., 2013).

6.2. High-throughput screening NM toxicity testing paradigm (Lai, 2012)

In 2012, D.Y. Lai from the US EPA presented a paradigm for NM toxicity testing that also puts emphasis on *in vitro* assays combined in a high-throughput screening platform. The testing paradigm further suggests selecting reference materials for different classes of NMs having unique physico-chemical characteristics, which may lead to different biological effects by different mechanisms of action. Accordingly, the NM testing paradigm consists of the following steps (Lai, 2012):

1. Assessment of toxicological effects of well-characterized reference NMs by short-term *in vivo* studies; investigation of molecular mechanisms underlying the effects; identification of key toxicity pathways by *in vivo* and *in vitro* high-throughput genomics or proteomics assays. In parallel, conduction of short-term *in vivo* studies to aid in interpretation of the responses and provide data for physiologically-based pharmacokinetics model development.
2. Testing of the reference materials by mechanism-based short-term *in vitro* assays using human cells or cell lines of target tissues to support interpretation of toxicity pathways. Again, the spectrum of selected assays, i.e. DCF-DA assays for oxidative stress/ROS, ELISA assay for cytokines, comet assays for DNA damage, TUNEL assays for apoptosis, etc., reflect important toxicity pathways recognized for NMs.
3. Evaluation of potential hazard of selected NMs of varying physico-chemical characteristics within class/subclass by conducting high-throughput *in vitro* assays and mechanism-based short-term *in vivo* assays and comparing data with those of reference materials of specific class/subclass.
4. Identification of physico-chemical parameter(s) and cut-off values of parameter(s) that contribute to toxicity of each NM class/subclass.

The NM testing paradigm has been put into practice in the context of the EPA's ToxCast™ HTS program. Wang et al. (2013a) tested 62 different NMs (mainly metal and metal oxide NMs and their ion and micron-scale counterparts and carbon nanotubes), taking into account potential exposure levels to determine test concentrations and using computational tools for organizing and analyzing data. Soluble NMs and their corresponding ions were found to have similar profiles, whereas different carbon nanotubes elicited different inflammatory profiles at non-cytotoxic concentrations. Overall, the core chemical composition of the given NM seemed to exert a greater influence on its biological effects than its size, but micron-scale materials were generally ranked lower than the corresponding NMs. Application of the HTS platform allowed prioritizing NMs for targeted testing, identifying affected biological pathways, and linking NM properties *in vitro* to potential *in vivo* effects (Wang et al., 2013b).

The need for a thorough assessment of the physico-chemical characteristics of NM is seen as a major obstacle in implementing HTS platforms. Particle characterization is time consuming and, additionally, might require larger amounts of test material than the test methods themselves (Wang et al., 2013a). To reduce the efforts for NM characterization, a 'minimal characterization' scheme is suggested including size distribution of primary particles and agglomerates, chemical composition (including surface and core, purity, and any impurities), surface area and reactivity, solubility/dissolution and stability. Additional characteristics might need to be assessed for specific types of NMs, e.g. crystallinity for TiO₂ NMs or dissolution properties for ion-shedding NMs, and particle characterization should further take into account that NM properties can change over time (Wang et al., 2013a).

6.3. Perturbational profiling of NM biological activity (Shaw et al., 2008)

Shaw et al. (2008) from Harvard University, USA, developed a systematic approach to comprehensively investigate *in vitro* NM effects by a so-called *perturbational profiling of NM biological activity*, i.e. a profiling of biological dysfunctions (perturbances). The set of *in vitro* assays covers different cell types (endothelial cells, smooth muscle cells, monocytes, hepatocytes) and includes the ATP assay, C12-resazurin assessment of reducing equivalents, caspase activation, and JC1 measurement of mitochondrial membrane potential. For each NM, multiple doses over a 30-fold concentration range are submitted to all possible assay combinations. Test results are expressed by a profile that jointly addresses applied dosage, cell type, and determined endpoint. These profiles are submitted to 'unsupervised hierarchical clustering' and 'consensus clustering' to identify NMs with similar patterns of biologic activity. 'Consensus clustering' implies iteratively repeating the hierarchical clustering algorithm with different data sub-samples thereby increasing the robustness of the clustering. The output of 'consensus clustering' is the fraction of clustering runs in which any two NMs cluster together. The greater the co-clustering frequency, the more likely it is that recognized clusters truly reflect an underlying structure (Shaw et al., 2008).

Shaw et al. applied the perturbational profiling approach to evaluate 50 different metal and metal oxide NMs possessing varying core compositions, coatings, and surface attachments. Overall, the NMs showed very divergent activity profiles. The clustering analyses yielded detailed structure–activity relationships and divided the set of NMs into three main clusters. Shaw et al. concluded that the biologic activity of NMs arises from the combined effects of many aspects of the NM composition. For the NMs tested, the core composition appeared to exert a strong (and unanticipated) influence on biologic activity. A subset of the 50 NMs was

tested in mice, and NMs with similar activity profiles *in vitro* exerted similar effects on *in vivo* monocyte numbers in the blood and spleen (Shaw et al., 2008).

6.4. Mechanism-based predictive testing approach (Cho et al., 2013)

Cho et al. (2013) from the University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom, suggest a mechanism-based predictive approach for the testing of ion shedding NMs and those acting via surface reactivity. The *in vitro* test systems cover 8 different cell-based assays including epithelial cells (A549 and 16HBE-cells), monocytic/macrophage cells (THP-1 cells, peripheral blood mononuclear cells), human erythrocytes, and combined cultures (subsequent treatment of first THP-1 and then A549 cells). *In vitro* toxicity endpoints comprise cytotoxicity (LDH release and trypan blue exclusion with or without addition of cytochalasin D to evaluate the role of phagocytosis), cytokine induction (interleukin-1beta, interleukin-8 and tumor necrosis factor-alpha), and hemolytic potential (determination of released hemoglobin). In putting the approach in practice, nine different NMs (CeO₂, TiO₂, carbon black, SiO₂, NiO, Co₃O₄, Cr₂O₃, CuO, and ZnO) were submitted to all combinations of the *in vitro* assays, and test results were compared with *in vivo* acute lung inflammogenicity in a rat instillation model at same surface area dosages (30 cm²/mL) of the test substances (Cho et al., 2013).

Acting via soluble toxic ions, NMs, such as ZnO or CuO, showed positive results in most *in vitro* assays, and the results were consistent with the lung inflammation data. Of the poorly soluble NMs acting via surface reactivity, only CeO₂ NMs elicited some degree of *in vitro* effects. Cytotoxicity in differentiated peripheral blood mononuclear cells was the most accurate *in vitro* parameter in predicting acute lung inflammogenicity (89% accuracy and 11% false negativity). The outcome of the hemolysis assay was 100% consistent with lung inflammation provided that any dose having statistical significance was assessed as 'positive' (Cho et al., 2013).

7. Summary and conclusion

To provide a basis for specific regulatory provisions for NM safety assessment, different countries and jurisdictions have laid down definitions of the term 'nanomaterial'. While the precise components of these definitions vary, all of them are based on material characteristics. However, the underlying nanomaterial properties are neither mono-causal, nor linearly related to the hazard or risk of NMs. Basing NM hazard and risk assessment on such material properties is likely to result in the over- or underestimation of hazards or failure to recognize relevant risks at all.

The grouping of substances is widely recognized as an important means to streamline toxicological testing for regulatory purposes. General grouping approaches for chemicals (not explicitly covering NMs) have already been implemented in, e.g., the EU REACH regulation. By contrast, to date there are no regulatory documents providing specific frameworks for the grouping of NMs in any of the jurisdictions evaluated in the present survey (i.e. EU, USA, Canada, Japan, or Australia). Nevertheless, the grouping of NMs is being addressed in publications from regulatory authorities or international research consortia, and preliminary guidance has been published in the context of substance-related legislation or in the occupational setting.

In their broad conceptual design, the evaluated approaches for the grouping of NMs are consistent or complement each other. Overall, the NM categories proposed in these concepts cover the range of aspects of NMs that have been recognized as relevant for NM hazard and risk assessment. For instance, material properties and biophysical interactions are addressed in the categorization scheme of the German Federal Institute for Occupational

Safety and Health (BAuA, 2013). NM exposure is a fundamental component of the grouping concepts of the US National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (Kuempel et al., 2012; DHHS (NIOSH), 2012). NM uptake is an integral part of the NanoDiv™ testing scheme (Anzai et al., 2012) or is addressed in the testing approach published by Monteiro-Riviere et al. (2011). Defined mechanisms of NM toxicity form the basis of the grouping and testing approaches published by Nel et al. (2013), Lai (2012), Shaw et al. (2008), or Cho et al. (2013). Furthermore, most NM categorizations are founded on quantifiable parameters (e.g. material properties and biophysical interactions) or the toxicological effects of the corresponding chemicals or larger particles of the same chemical composition (which can be assessed in accepted test methods).

In summary, all of the available proposals for the grouping of NMs already go beyond the determination of mere (quantitative) structure–activity relationships. They are founded on different aspects of the NM life cycle, even though none of the proposals fully takes into account all relevant parameters. Most of the grouping approaches cover different material properties, some the toxicological effects of the corresponding bulk materials or, less frequently, toxicological MoAs of the NMs. NM exposure and use scenarios are only occasionally addressed. Nevertheless, by founding NM grouping on different combinations of relevant aspects of a NM's life cycle, the spectrum of available concepts for the grouping of NMs forms a sound scientific basis to advance regulatory provisions on the grouping of NMs. Future research should aim at combining the available concepts into a comprehensive 'multiple perspective' framework for the grouping of NMs.

This comprehensive, 'multiple perspective' framework should take into account the pathway from the release of the NM to the apical toxic effect. The concept should address the different stages of the NM's life cycle, since risks can change, e.g. once a nanofirm powder is embedded in a composite. The 'multiple perspective' framework should consider NM material properties and biophysical interactions, their use and exposure, their uptake and kinetics, just as possible early and apical biological effects. In this respect, however, a 'multiple perspective' approach does not imply fixed testing schemes for all NMs in all applications. On the contrary, such 'tick-box' testing would result in the collection of vast amounts of scientifically unnecessary information, which is neither desirable on animal welfare grounds, nor for economic reasons. Instead, a comprehensive 'multiple perspective' grouping approach that is closely linked to IATAs by supporting a concern-driven stepwise collection and evaluation of information that is truly relevant for the given purpose is recommended for use. In the second part of its assignment, the ECETOC TF on grouping and IATAs of nanomaterials will put forward a proposal for such a comprehensive 'multiple perspective' grouping approach.

To ensure its practicality, the 'multiple perspective' NM grouping framework should indicate specific test methods that allow generating the necessary data to assign NMs to the different groups and that is required for a concern-driven ranking of NMs within a group or between different groups of NMs. In this respect, high throughput screening platforms and the computational evaluation of data appear important tools to address NM complexity during grouping or hazard assessment. A further challenge lies in defining criteria to justify the assignment of a NM to a group of similar concern. For this purpose, case studies should be initiated to verify the quality and robustness of the grouping framework, since most of the currently available approaches have not yet advanced beyond theoretical, conceptual stages.

Overall, a comprehensive, 'multiple perspective' NM grouping framework, linked to concern-driven IATAs, serves to streamline testing to the collection of data that is relevant for NM safety assessment. Since the 'multiple perspective' framework is founded

on scientifically justifiable categories, safe uses of NMs can be identified and unsafe uses excluded. Finally, the 'multiple perspective' NM grouping framework allows assessing NMs economically and in a timesaving manner and contributes to replacing, reducing, and refining the need for animal testing (Russell and Burch, 1959).

Conflict of interest

This manuscript was prepared by members of the ECETOC Task Force on nanomaterials. TP represents and JA, MH, RK, DL, MM, KM, DW, KW, RL are employees of companies producing and/or marketing nanomaterials. UGS was hired by ECETOC to support this Task Force. The authors alone are responsible for the content and writing of the paper.

Acknowledgments

We thank the members of the ECETOC Scientific Committee for their feedback. Special thanks go to Dr. Alan Poole, Secretary General of ECETOC, and Ms. Christine Yannakas of ECETOC for their extensive administrative support. RL received funding from the EU FP7 project MARINA.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.yrtph.2014.07.025>.

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